

Wall-pressure measurements in a Mach 2 Turbulent SBLI by Means of a Flexible PVDF Piezo-Film Sensor Array.

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A novel flexible unsteady wall-pressure sensor array based on piezoelectric PVDF films has been developed and tested in a turbulent SBLI configuration at Mach 2. Compared to the previous version, the new sensor’s flexibility makes it easier to fit on different surfaces, while offering enhanced durability and improved sensitivity. The array consists of 18 circular sensors with a diameter of 3 mm manufactured with screen printing techniques from a PVDF film of 110 μm thickness. It provides excellent spatial resolution and minimal flow intrusiveness at a fraction of the cost of traditional dynamic pressure transducers. The sensor array was dynamically calibrated with a ball-drop impact test device and tested in a supersonic wind tunnel, showing good agreement with the reference measurements taken with a state-of-the-art Kulite pressure sensor. The obtained $f \cdot PSD$ distributions match the results found in the literature, with the low-frequency unsteadiness region under the separation shock foot ($X^* = 0$) characterized by a Strouhal range of $St = 0.03 - 0.05$.

Nomenclature

M	= Mach number	x_0	= Separation onset location
V	= Voltage	x_{imp}	= Inviscid shock impingement point
RMS	= Root Mean Square value	L_{sep}	= Separation length
Re_U	= Freestream unit Reynolds number	L_{int}	= Interaction length
S	= Separation Point	Q	= Generated charge
R	= Reattachment Point	σ_n	= Mechanical stress
PVDF	= Polyvinylidene fluoride	D	= Charge density
t	= Thickness	St	= Strouhal number
E	= Young’s module	ϵ/ϵ_0	= Relative permittivity
d_{3n}	= Piezoelectric constant	DAQ	= Data Acquisition System
δ_0	= Boundary layer velocity thickness	SG	= Shock Generator
g	= Gravitational constant	BL	= Boundary Layer
f	= Frequency	σ^2	= Variance of the time signal
f_s	= Sampling Frequency	N	= Number of Samples

I. Introduction

Shockwave boundary layer interactions (SBLIs) represent an ongoing topic of research, due to their complex flow structure and the rising interest in supersonic flow applications. A critical aspect of this phenomena is their natural unsteadiness, which is manifested by an oscillation of the shockwave at frequencies significantly lower than the turbulent fluctuations in the incoming boundary layer, particularly evident when the latter separates due to the strong adverse pressure gradient caused by the incident shock.[1] This high-amplitude, low-frequency unsteadiness has a major role in

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Fig. 1 Piezofilm sensor setup.[8]

industry applications, since it underlies a number of problems such as structural failures, panel flutter and self-induced instabilities like buffet and inlet buzz[2–4]. Even though a wide body of research on turbulent SBLIs has been conducted in the past decades[5], the mechanisms behind the low-frequency unsteadiness is still not fully understood and there is still debate between two major potential causes. One of the proposed mechanisms is the upstream one, where the source of the unsteadiness comes from the presence of low-frequency flow structures in the incoming turbulent boundary layer [6]; a second, downstream mechanism, relates the fluctuations of the separation shock to the periodic contraction and expansion in a breathing motion of the separation bubble [7].

A common method to experimentally investigate the low-frequency unsteadiness in separated SBLIs is through measurement of wall-pressure fluctuations under the separated shock foot. Most researchers to date have used piezo-resistive pressure transducers (often *XCQ series Kulites*[®]) [2]. They are well known for their high accuracy and sensitivity. However, when it comes to measuring spatial wall-pressure correlations, Kulites have a significant disadvantage in that they require simultaneous acquisition of multiple sensors. This means that a large number of sensors must be placed in the facility, which in turn increases the cost of the experimental setup.

In a previous work we developed a novel non-invasive and cost-effective technique for SBLI unsteady wall-pressure measurements based on a piezo-film sensor array.[8] This film sensors are based on the organic polymer *polyvinylidene fluoride* (PVDF) whose piezoelectric proprieties have been discovered for the first time by Kawai in 1969 [9]. The piezoelectric proprieties (change in surface-charge caused by mechanical loading of the film) are due to the particular crystalline disposition that the polymer acquires after artificial polarization. The PVDF layer is double-side coated with a thin layer of metal, so that the charges generated by the external forces through the piezoelectric effect of the material are collected on the 2 faces of the film. The metal coating layer can be partially etched into custom shapes and patterns keeping only a wanted portion of the metal. In such a way it is possible to form specific arrays of active sensor with virtually as many point as required from just a single foil. Figure 1 shows a schematic of the setup of a PVDF sensor, with some example of etched arrays obtained by removing the coating from one side (figure 1b), or from both sides (figure 1c). In figure 1a the signal chain is shown: the application of external forces causes a charge build-up in the foil that it's acquired by means of a charge amplifier which transforms the charges collected on the metal faces into a voltage signal detectable by the DAQ. An important aspect is that, because of the capacitive behaviour of the PVDF material, charges generated on the two electrodes slowly cancel each other. This implies that this kind of sensor is only capable of detecting pressure fluctuations (AC signal) and not the mean static pressure field.

The previous sensor design studied by Corsi et al. [8] faced a significant issue with its rigid packaging, which resulted in the loss of some critical benefits of piezofolios, such as flexibility and low intrusiveness. Moreover, the rigid setup's instrumentation was complex, and the signal chain lacked robustness, particularly concerning the connection of the sensor with the acquisition system. To overcome these challenges, this paper presents the results of the development and testing of a novel PVDF flexible sensor array. Our primary goal is to demonstrate its potential for unsteady wall-pressure

M	Re_U	δ_0	Shock generator angle	Test section dimensions
2	$12.5 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^{-1}$	7.2 mm	6° - 10°	150 mm x 150 mm

Table 1 Supersonic wind tunnel parameters.[10]

investigations in complex flow fields, such as SBLI studies. Thus we will validate the sensor's performance against state-of-the-art Kulite pressure sensors, which are widely used in aerodynamic research.

II. Experimental Setup

A. Test Facility and Test Case Arrangement

The experimental investigations were conducted at the Chair of Aerodynamics of *Technische Universität Berlin* in a supersonic wind tunnel. An in-depth review of the facility is presented by Rohlfs et al. [10], and a schematic representation is shown in figure 2. The tunnel operates continuously with an indraft mechanism: the air is sucked in by a centrifugal compressor, driven up to 16 000 rpm by a 400 kW electric DC motor. The air then passes through a heated drying chamber in the laboratory's basement, and after passing the settling chamber and screens for turbulence reduction, it enters inside the test section, which is composed of a Mach 2 supersonic nozzle and a shock generator used to create an incident SBLI with the (turbulent) floor boundary layer. The main characteristics of the wind tunnel and test section are presented in table 1.

The turbulent shockwave boundary layer interaction being studied is produced using a shock generator with a deflection angle of 10 degrees. This creates an oblique shock that interacts with a fully turbulent boundary layer of thickness $\delta_0 = 7.2 \text{ mm}$ on the wind-tunnel floor. The flow topology of interest is depicted in Figure 3: an oblique shockwave impinges on a fully turbulent boundary layer, creating a strong adverse pressure gradient. This leads to the formation of a separation bubble with reversed flow between the *separation point S* and the *reattachment point R*, with a characteristic length L_{sep} . The curvature of the bubble induces converging compression waves in the incoming flow that merge into a *separation shock*, interacting with the incident shock, and forming the characteristic λ -foot of the separated SBLI. Another important parameter to consider for the following investigations is the interaction length L_{int} defined as the distance between the extrapolated impingement point x_{imp} (from inviscid shock theory) and the interaction onset x_0 where the wall pressure starts to rise.

Fig. 2 Schematic representation of the supersonic wind tunnel present at *TU Berlin* with a focus on the turbulent SBLI test section.[10]

t	d_{33}	E	ϵ/ϵ_0	Freq. Range	Dynamic Range	T Range
$110 \mu\text{m}$	$33 \times 10^{-12} \text{ C/N}$	$4 \times 10^9 \text{ Pa}$	12	$10^{-3}-10^{10} \text{ Hz}$	$10^{-5}-10^9 \text{ Pa}$	$-40 \text{ to } 80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$

Table 2 Typical characteristics of PVDF piezo-films.[11]

B. Piezofoil Sensor Array

1. Piezofoil Design

For the purpose of this study, a clean polarized PVDF film with a thickness of $110 \mu\text{m}$ was used. The main properties of the film are presented in table 2 [11]. It is important to note that while the frequency and dynamic ranges shown in the table are strictly properties of the material, the actual values of the final sensors depend on the entire signal chain, from the charge amplifier to the DAQ system, as we will discuss later.

As already introduced previously, the working principle of this type of piezoelectric sensor is based on the charge produced inside the semicrystalline structure of the PVDF by an external mechanical stress. The generated charge density D , in absence of an external electrical field, can be expressed as:

$$D = \sum d_{3n} \sigma_{3n} \quad (n = 1, 2, 3) \quad (1)$$

where d_{3n} and σ_{3n} are respectively the piezoelectric constant and the mechanical stress along the direction n , where 1 = length, 2 = width, 3 = thickness. In the present study we are interested in the pressure fluctuation applied on the sensor, hence $n = 3$ (normal stress). Furthermore we assume that the shear stress fluctuations ($n = 2, 3$) can be neglected [12]. So, considering only the 3rd direction and multiplying equation 1 by the active area A , which is the sensitive part of the sensor where the positive and negative electrodes overlap, we obtain the value of the charge Q generated by the sensor:

$$D = d_{33} \sigma_{33} \quad \Rightarrow \quad Q = DA = d_{33} \sigma_{33} A \quad (2)$$

from equation 2 evaluations on the spatial resolution can be made: ideally the smallest possible sensor size should be chosen for the best resolution, however a sensing area too small wouldn't produce enough charges for a good signal to noise ratio. Furthermore, the size of the sensor has also an influence on the frequency response, because the high frequency range of the spectrum is generated by the smallest fluid structures, so if the sensor size is larger than the flow structures it will filter their contribution and the high frequency response will be attenuated.

Figure 4 displays the final design. The sensor array includes 18 circular sensors, 6 of which are arranged in the streamwise direction and 3 positioned along the span. Each sensing element has a diameter of 3 mm, and the full sensor covers a surface area of $50 \times 18 \text{ mm}^2$. The pitch between consecutive sensing points along the streamwise direction is 10 mm, while the spacing across the spanwise direction is 6 mm. Figure 4a depicts the design of the developed

Fig. 3 Representation of a separated shockwave-boundary interaction, adapted from [1]. The white circles are representing the positions of the PVDF sensors.

Fig. 4 Flexible piezofoil array: (a) structure of the proposed sensor; (b) final setup with connection interface for charge amplifier.

array, which is composed of a multilayered structure consisting of the following components: a Flex-PCB, a 3M™ 9703 anisotropic conductive adhesive, and the PVDF piezoelectric active layer with its silver electrode array. The Flex-PCB provides support for the entire sensor and is custom patterned with Ag-ink to create contact pads and wires for connecting the sensors to the acquisition system. The 3M™ 9703 layer is a special anisotropic conductive adhesive layer that contains silver nanoparticles dispersed, and provides electrical conductivity between the Flex-PCB and the PVDF layer. The PVDF layer itself is the active part of the sensor, consisting of both the piezoelectrically active layer and the silver electrode array.

The sensor production process for the PVDF and the FlexPCB layers has been carried out in the laboratory of *Hochschule für Technik und Wirtschaft Berlin*. The manufacturing process starts with the clean substrate (i.e. the polarized PVDF or the PE sheet), which is then patterned on both sides using screen printing techniques with silver ink. This process involves creating a stencil of the desired pattern, which is then placed on the substrate film. The silver ink is then applied through the stencil onto the film using a squeegee, resulting in a precise and repeatable pattern on the surface of the film. Once the patterning is complete, the patterned material is heated allowing the metallic ink to cure and improve its electrical and mechanical properties. This process can be easily and quickly adapted to produce pattern of varying sizes and shapes, making it a versatile method for creating sensors for a various range of applications.

A challenging aspect of the instrumentation concerns finding the proper connection setup for the sensor. This step is critical, since the appropriate interface between the metal coatings of the piezofilm and the signal conditioning system is needed in order to prevent unwanted noises and signal degradation. Various ways of creating connections from the PVDF's electrodes exist. For this study a Flexible Flat Cable (FFC) connector is used. The latter is a ribbon like connectors, made of flexible plastic, polymers, films, or engineered rubber and have a metallic connector at the end, which is embedded in parallel to the base and allows a very sleek integration with the signal conditioning system (figure 4b).

The final sensor is glued flush to the test section floor and thanks to the flexibility and low thickness of the foil, the connection interface is mounted outside of the test section sending the signal to the charge amplifier for the conditioning.

The new piezoelectric PVDF flexible sensor array presented in this paper offers several advantages over the old rigid one shown by Corsi et al. [8]. Firstly, the new sensor is much more flexible than the previous rigid design, which allows for greater versatility in the experimental setup. This flexibility allows the sensor to be more easily bent and shaped to conform to the surface on which it is placed, thus improving its accuracy in measuring pressure in complex flow fields. Secondly, the improved robustness of the new sensor is a significant advantage. The use of an FFC (Flexible Flat Cable) connector ensures a secure and reliable connection between the sensor and the data acquisition system, reducing the risk of signal loss and interference. This improved connection setup also makes the array easier to use and maintain, as the FFC connector allows for quick and easy connection and disconnection from the amplification and data acquisition system.

Op-Amp	C_f	R_f	R_i	C_p	f_L
TLC-272	100 pF	100 M Ω	56 Ω	10 pF	15.9 Hz

Table 3 Charge amplifier design parameters.

Fig. 5 Electrical circuit of a charge amplifier and its frequency response.[13]

2. Signal Conditioning and Acquisition System

The direct output voltage measured from the piezo sensors is typically only a few mV. Thus, to obtain a readable signal with good SNR, a proper amplification system is required. Due to the high impedance of PVDF, a high-impedance amplifier is necessary, and in this work, a charge amplifier has been chosen. Figure 5 shows the electrical circuit of a typical charge amplifier and its frequency response. One advantage of using a charge amplifier is that the output voltage is solely dependent on the feedback capacitance C_f (i.e., $V_o = -Q/C_f$) and not on the cable capacitance (C_c) or sensor capacitance (C_p), enabling the use of longer cables and minimizing charge leakage [11]. To optimize the performance of our PVDF sensors, the charge amplifier was designed using the components specified in Table 3. The central component of the system is the *Texas Instruments*TM TLC-272 operational amplifier, a CMOS single-supply amplifier with a low offset voltage drift, high input impedance, and low noise behavior. The feedback capacitor C_f is used to balance the charges injected into the negative input of the Op-Amp, while the resistor R_f prevents the amplifier from drifting into saturation by slowly bleeding the charge off the feedback capacitor. The values of C_f and R_f determine the low cutoff frequency of the charge amplifier, which can be calculated as $f_L = \frac{1}{2\pi R_f C_f}$. In our case, these values result in a cutoff frequency of $f_L = 15.9$ Hz. The high cutoff frequency $f_H = \frac{1}{2\pi R_i (C_p + C_c)}$ is set by the resistor R_i , which also provides electrostatic discharge (ESD) protection. The capacitance of the sensor (C_p) and cable (C_c) also contribute to this frequency, but it is well beyond the frequency range of interest, in the MHz range [13].

The signal acquisition is carried out by means of a *National Instruments*TM NI-USB 6353 data acquisition card, in order to obtain PSDs up to 100 kHz a sample rate of $f_s = 200$ kHz for $N = 200000$ samples with a resulting period of $T = N/f_s = 1$ s was used.

3. Frequency Response Evaluation

In order to evaluate the dynamic response of the sensor together with the signal chain, a source signal with a known frequency response is needed. An ideal calibration source should impose a unidirectional force acting on a small region of the test specimen and should produce a smooth and broad range of frequencies. For this study an impact ball-drop test was performed: this is an impulsive (step-like) source producing a wide frequency range signal. The setup adopted for the calibration testing is shown in figure 6c and it involves a 3D printed support holding the plug, instrumented with the PVDF sensor, and a 30mm tube. The support is equipped with a traverse system allowing the possibility of testing each sensor of the array. A small steel ball with a diameter of $R_1 = 2.4$ mm is dropped onto the specimen from the tube height of $h = 30$ mm. The ball's impact on the specimen produces a force with an impulse-like effect. This force can be precisely calculated using Hertzian theory, and is accurately modeled by a forcing function $f(t)$: [14, 15]

$$f(t) = \begin{cases} F_{max} \sin(\pi t/t_c)^{3/2}, & t \in [0, t_c] \\ 0, & t \in (t_c, \infty) \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where $F_{max} = 1.917\rho_1^{3/5}(\delta_1 + \delta_2)^{-2/5}R_1^2v_0^{6/5}$ is the maximum force, $t_c = 4.53(4/3\rho_1\pi(\delta_1 + \delta_2))^{-2/5}R_1v_0^{-1/5}$ is the

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 6 Ball-drop impact test results: (a) theoretical impulse generated by the impact (red dashed line) and signal measured by the PVDF sensor (black solid line);(b) FFT spectra of the acquired signal (black solid line) compared to the theoretical one;(c) setup adopted for the ball drop impact test.

time the ball spends in contact with the sensor during the impact, while $\delta_i = (1 - \mu^2 / \pi E_i)$ with E_i and μ_i Young's module and Poisson ratio of the materials. Subscripts $i = 1$ represent the steel ball and $i = 2$ the material of the more massive test specimen (the instrumented plug). Finally R_1 is the radius and $v_0 = \sqrt{2gh}$ the impact speed of the steel ball.

In figure 6a the impulsive time signal generated by the ball impact is shown for both experimental (black) and theoretical (red) cases, while in figure 6b the amplitude of the Fourier transform spectra is displayed. In red the spectra of the source function $f(t)$ is shown, this is characterized by a series of lobes separated by zeros at higher frequencies, while being flat at low frequencies. Due to the low Young's module E_2 of the plug material the contact time t_c is relatively high, and thus the cutoff frequency of the steel ball spectra is at around $f_0 = 25\,000$ Hz. The experimental results obtained with the PVDF sensor are matching the theoretical results well, which validates the assumption of the flat frequency response of the piezofoil, at least up to f_0 . Further experiments with stiffer plug materials will be carried out in the future in order to validate the sensor response for higher frequencies.

III. Results

In the following section the results obtained with the novel flexible sensor are introduced. The sensor arrangement under the SBLI flow is represented in figure 3:

- Position 1-2: in proximity of the interaction onset location x_0 , under the λ -shock foot;
- Position 3-6: under the separation bubble.

Figure 7a displays the time signals obtained at each position, as described previously. For the sake of simplicity and due to limitations in the data acquisition (DAQ) system, only one sensor out of the three per row is presented instead of the full array of 18 piezo sensors. The amplitude variation along the streamwise direction is immediately noticeable. Specifically, the root-mean-square (RMS) of the signal increases as the position moves towards the end of the interaction, owing to the developing shear layer behind the separation bubble. This outcome is consistent with the previous experiment conducted by Corsi et al. [16] in the same facility with kulite transducers. Moreover, the sensitivity of the new flexible sensor design appears to be enhanced compared to the previous rigid sensor design. Indeed, the amplitude obtained using the old sensor in [8] were significantly lower than those obtained with the new design.

The Power Spectral Density (PSD) plots in Figure 7b were obtained by applying Welch's method to the time traces, using 20 Hanning windows with 75% overlap. However, interpreting the PSD spectra alone does not provide a clear understanding of the flow unsteadiness. To better characterize the flow, the normalized premultiplied PSD ($PSD(f)f/\sigma^2$) was computed. The normalization was done through the variance σ^2 of the time signal. The frequency f was normalized with the Strouhal number ($St_L = fL_{int}/u_\infty$), where L_{int} is the length of the separation region, and u_∞ is the free-stream velocity. Finally the streamwise length was normalized with the separation length as $X^=(x - x_0)/L_{int}$, where x is the streamwise position and x_0 is the position of the interaction onset.

The results obtained from the piezofilm array are presented in figure 8 in the form of normalized premultiplied PSD distributions. These plots provide valuable insights into the energy content of the flow at different frequencies and locations of the SBLI. As expected, the typical patterns observed in the literature [2, 8, 10, 16–19] are visible, with distinct frequency ranges divided into different zones, each with its own temporal scales.

- The first zone, known as the low frequency zone (LFZ), is located at the beginning of the interaction region near the foot of the reflected shock, around $X^* \approx 0$. The LFZ is characterized by very low frequency fluctuations with a broad hump centered at $St_L \approx 0.04 - 0.05$. This hump is a clear indication of the large-scale, low-frequency motion of the reflected shock.
- The second zone, named intermediate frequency zone (IFZ), corresponds to the interaction zone $-0.2 \leq X^* \leq 1$, with spectra showing a medium-frequency character at $St_L \approx 1$. Such IFZ typically represents the pressure signature of large-scale coherent structures that are shed downstream of the separation bubble.

Figure 8 also shows the comparison between the ($f \cdot PSD$) obtained with the novel PVDF sensors and the ones obtained with a state-of-the-art Kulite pressure transducer. The Kulite used is the fast response piezoresistive transducer, XCQ-062, whose signal was passed through an hardware low-pass filter with a cut-off frequency of $f_L = 100$ kHz. The Kulite was mounted flush with the floor of the test section and the acquisitions were taken sequentially for each position corresponding to the PVDF array ones. The signal was acquired with the same DAQ as the piezofilm, and the data were processed with the same parameters. The results indicate that the newly developed piezofilm sensors are able to match the Kulite data quite precisely, and to accurately capture the unsteady characteristics of the various flow regions. Specifically, both the LFZ and the IFZ are well captured by the piezofilm sensors. Inside the IFZ, several sharp peaks are observed on the PVDF spectra only. These peaks are likely due to acoustic interference caused by air leaks in proximity of the instrumented plug. The PVDF sensors, which have higher sensitivity compared to the Kulite, are able to capture these acoustic interferences. Therefore, it is essential to ensure that the wind tunnel is properly sealed and there are no air leaks that could generate interferences. Despite these peaks, the results demonstrate the high fidelity and reliability of the PVDF sensors in capturing the dynamic behavior of the flow field.

IV. Conclusion

A novel flexible unsteady wall-pressure sensor array based on piezoelectric PVDF films has been developed and tested in a turbulent SBLI configuration at Mach 2. Compared to the previous rigid design shown by Corsi et al. [8], the new sensor's flexibility makes it possible to fit it on complicated surfaces, thus enabling pressure measurements in more complex flow geometries. Furthermore it offers enhanced robustness, ease of implementation, and improved sensitivity. The array consists of 18 circular sensors with a diameter of 3 mm manufactured with screen printing techniques from a PVDF film of 110 μm thickness. The array provide excellent spatial resolution and minimal flow intrusiveness at a fraction of the cost of traditional dynamic pressure transducers. The sensor was dynamically calibrated with a ball drop

Fig. 7 (a) Time signals acquired by the PVDF array across the turbulent SBLI; (b) relative Power Spectral Densities for each streamwise position obtained from the PVDF measurements

Fig. 8 Frequency domain results obtained in a Mach 2 turbulent SBLI obtained with a 10° shock generator: (a) comparison between Kulita (red) and Piezofoil (black) $f * PSD$ spectra of the acquired signal for every streamwise position across the SBLI; (b) $f * PSD$ map distribution obtained with the PVDF-array; (c) $f * PSD$ map distribution obtained with the Kulite sensor.

impact test device, showing a flat response throughout the range generated by the ball impulse up to $f = 25\,000$ Hz. The results of the multi-point surface measurement showed a good agreement with the reference measurements taken with a state-of-the-art Kulite pressure sensor, confirming the validity of the proposed sensor array for unsteady wall pressure measurements. The obtained $f \cdot PSD$ distributions showed good agreement with the results found in the literature, with the low-frequency unsteadiness region under the separation shock foot ($X^* = 0$) characterized by a Strouhal range of $St = 0.03 - 0.05$. These results demonstrate the potential of using the new sensor array for unsteadiness studies where good spatial resolution and low intrusiveness are needed, such as in SBLI flows. For future works, spatial cross correlation investigations will be carried out across both streamwise and spanwise directions under the SBLI, to fully exploit the high spatial resolution and the simultaneous acquisition capabilities of the sensor array. Overall, the proposed PVDF flexible sensor represents a promising and cost-effective alternative to conventional dynamic pressure transducers, offering improved flexibility, robustness, and sensitivity for unsteady wall pressure measurements in complex flow fields.

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